

Sustain Sahel

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Deliverable 8.1 Communication & Dissemination Strategy

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1. Introduction

This document outlines the elements concerning the planning for and execution of Communications & Dissemination actions designed to support delivery of the expected impacts of SustainSahel.

This strategy is a **living document** which will be monitored on an on-going basis, updated to include detail on timings, contacts, meetings and emerging opportunities as the project develops and the operational WPs establish their protocols at field, regional and national levels. The Strategy will be formally reviewed at two more points during the funded period – at months 35 and 54 – and revised as appropriate, taking progress, and set targets into account. This allows the evolution of dissemination tools to fit with project developments (results and other outcomes availability), and to the multi-actor expectations.

The current version of the document is the first one after the restructuring of WVP8 and the consequent change of leadership. These changes provided an opportunity to bring more attention to areas that were previously insufficiently addressed, such as the local dissemination and a stronger articulation between all of the project mechanisms and activities that relate to knowledge transfer and sharing.

2. Objectives

SustainSahel seeks to enhance the resilience of farming systems in the Sahel through the study and dissemination of appropriate crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices. This is achieved through a transdisciplinary approach: the integration of social and natural sciences in close collaboration with smallholder farmers. Work Package 8, in close collaboration with the other WPs of SustainSahel, has several core objectives to disseminate the project's results in an optimum way. These objectives include:

- Multi-directional communication and dissemination strategy, utilising diverse and appropriate communication channels for the targeted stakeholder groups;
- Work with innovations coming out of other work packages to and to develop relevant and accessible content for all target stakeholders disseminated across and beyond the project's channels
- Provide knowledge exchange/transfer, uptake of opportunities and utilisation of project results, recommendations and materials by target groups at regional, national, European and international levels;
- Disseminate appropriate crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices in the seven project sites of the project, through farmer field days, radio broadcasts, visits to demonstration plots and the use of information and communication technologies;
- Promote a close collaboration with the process of the innovation platforms and the growing communities of practice, therefore embedding the project learnings via multi-actor networks;
- To work closely with WP2 and WP3, which will assess the socio-economic impact of the disseminated crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices;
- To empower smallholder farmers to become the owners and disseminators of the practices themselves, in all of the project sites;
- Meet with policy, research and practice-oriented agencies and influencers - provide informed policy recommendations for the design of policies to overcome obstacles and increase the adoption of sustainable intensification;

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- Use of existing communication channels at a national and European level and to ensure the long-term availability of materials
- Collaborate and exchange with other relevant EU/AU initiatives, i.e., FAIR Sahel, EWA-BELT, etc.
- Improve scientific knowledge and generate an updated state of the art regarding the CSL systems

3. Target groups

Dissemination measures will address the full range of potential users and uses, including research and the whole value chain related to sustainable intensification in SustainSahel's focus countries:

- Farmers, extension workers,
- Value-chain/market actors,
- Public authorities and policymakers,
- Scientific community, including students,
- The media and general public, e.g., consumers

In order to successfully reach these diverse target groups listed above, and have tangible impact, action is required at six distinct levels:

1. **Local level:** the dissemination of appropriate practices is one of the core cross-WP activities in the project, involving all actors and a very close collaboration between farmers' organizations and research institutions in each partner country. With local multi-actors and organisations actively engaged in activities and knowledge acquisition/exchange supported by partners on the ground as they establish the Innovation Platforms;
2. **National level:** Engagement with relevant stakeholder organisations in the countries in which SustainSahel is active, taking advantage of existing networks, fora, and established meetings;
3. **Pan-African level:** Raise awareness of SustainSahel vision and actions to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration with existing networks, fora and events;
4. **Project level:** with all project partners actively engaged in WP8 and its actions to drive awareness across all interested and relevant parties including the wider public;
5. **European level:** Active engagement with aligned projects, agencies, and initiatives to collaborate and exchange knowledge, experience, and insights, together with direct and ongoing exchange with EU funding agencies and fora;
6. **International level:** by aligning communications with the Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs) and the UN's operational groups, taking opportunities to present and exchange knowledge and insights with other appropriate international organisations, events and meetings.

Communication and dissemination tools and approaches used for all dissemination levels will ensure reaching out to different target groups within each level. To reach the target groups, tailored formats will be produced (see chapters 4 and 5).

Four communication principles to reach the target groups

Throughout Communications & Dissemination planning and implementation the following four principles have priority consideration in order to drive the delivery of impact:

1. **Language** – dual English & French will be used throughout and as appropriate to drive understanding and inclusion. Further local languages will be utilised as advised and considered necessary.
2. **Inclusivity & diversity** – gender and age group representation (youth in particular) will be catered for across all materials, events, and actions to ensure all are acknowledged, heard and involved in co-creation events and initiatives
3. **Accessibility & relevance** – collateral will be produced in visual formats and in language that is accessible to all, utilising most commonly used technologies and formats such as mobile phones utilising bluetooth
4. **Support from & to all partners & across WPs** – critical to success as these actions will ‘feed’ the flow of information to communications actions & materials & engage stakeholders at all levels

4. Formats and tools for project promotion and communication

The project consortium is committed to delivering communication activities that satisfy both the general and contractual commitment to provide information to the public about the focus and achievements of publicly funded research, as well as the promotion of new technologies and dissemination of knowledge to potential users of that knowledge for utilization across different sectors and for possible exploitation.

Therefore, the social, environmental, economic, political, commercial, and scientific value of the project outputs will be explained using clear messages that can engage with each of the target audiences. Actions have been selected and designed to identify and engage on the one hand, directly with stakeholders that have the potential to influence policy to support the implementation of the new knowledge and practices generated, and on the other to deliver effective outreach to our end-user communities.

In addition, the actions will also fulfil the project’s contractual obligations to ensure that the ‘wider public’ and specifically parties with an interest in its aims and objectives, but without a specific mandate to operate in this area, have the ability to stay fully informed of the project’s work.

Table I summarises the main communications actions, together with purpose, targets, objectives and initial measures of success. The focus and nature of these actions will be monitored on an ongoing basis via the detailed ‘real time’ Action Plan with formal assessment as part of the strategic review at months 35 and 56.

Table I. Core communications activities, aims & progress measures

Description	Aims	Current status
Strategic communication and dissemination plan		
A working document for core WP8 partners that identifies priority stakeholders, targeted messaging, channels to utilise to connect, relevant collateral	To provide a strategic plan against which to review and revise actions as well as evaluate new opportunities for communication and	Drafted and reviewed at M35 and M56

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material to produce, methods of recording successful engagement	engagement actions with specific stakeholder groups as they arise	
Visual identity (Brand)		
Materials for partners and all WPs to drive for project visibility: Logo, icon, color palette and templates as explained in D8.5 'Project logo, artwork/design User Manual & template'	To build common identity for the project, its brand, plus awareness, trust in and reputation of the work of Sustain Sahel.	Finished and shared with all SS partners
Project outreach materials		
Project poster/banners, infographics, promotional videos, t-shirts, pens, etc.	Drive engagement with all targeted stakeholders and secure set objectives	Finished: SS promo video, poster, bookmarks In development: t-shirts, caps, pens, etc.
Project website and newsletter		
For partners and all stakeholders: Provision of a website – the window for the world onto the project – populated by a variety of relevant visual, video/audio content; plus, a regularly issued newsletter housed on the website and sent direct to a GDPR compliant database	To provide a portal via which all specialist and lay audiences can view the project mission, progress and results and access and download information as required. The website is available in both French and English. Content is generated according to an editorial schedule and adapted according to project needs and outputs	Website Established and constantly updated according to the editorial schedule and project needs Newsletter Sent 3x annual
Social media channels		
These channels allow the project to reach out to a variety of stakeholders.	To network and engage target groups active on social media. Social media will be used as an essential tool in the communications toolbox.	Social media accounts have been set up and are actively managed
Media communications		
Creation of international media database, issue of regular media releases, provision of prepared articles and content for journalists and channels. Social media accounts to capture and	To cascade information and news as widely as possible utilising effective gatekeepers and multipliers in the media. Produced articles will be comprehensive and placed into the public domain.	Two press releases have been sent, and more are planned in the coming months. The media database is being further developed for each focus country.

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engage with wide range of inclusive and diverse content		
Collaborations with related projects and organisations		
Connect with related projects organisations, platforms, political and advisory groups and networks at international, European, pan-African, regional, national, and local levels. For a detailed list of WP8 partnerships, refer to Table A-1 and A-2 in the Annex	Build on existing networks, dissemination infrastructures, allied projects and initiatives centred on CSL systems, thus avoiding duplicating work and instigating parallel networks. Co-create, co-deliver or amplify messages	Links have been developed via communications exchanges and social media channels, and direct relationships are underway with many targeted initiatives.
Networking, raising awareness of SustainSahel with EC		
Direct communication of project outputs during direct meetings with EC, appropriate DGs and agencies policy-makers (key players in embedding new practices into action).	Strengthening policy-advocacy dialogue with key EU relevant actors to promote SustainSAHEL's results that feed into policy -making	First discussions with DG INTPA have occurred to organise a first session on mid.term key results of the project

5. Formats and tools for the dissemination of SustainSahel results to the target groups

The stronger focus on local dissemination and on the articulation between different project mechanisms that promote knowledge transfer and co-creation means that the end users of the project's main results are at the core of its dissemination strategy. A number of formats are being used to disseminate the SustainSahel results, seeking not only to inform and engage smallholder farmers but also to empower them as the owners and disseminators of the co-created and transferred knowledge.

FiBL, CSE, and the local farmers' organizations have collaborated closely together to elaborate the local dissemination action plan (see Annex B), which brings all stakeholders into a continuous learning process that put farmers and their experiences at its core. The research institutions have also contributed, bringing their perspectives and knowledge production approaches into the discussion. Bi-weekly meetings with farmers' organizations during the first and second trimesters of 2022 resulted in a common approach in the three countries regarding the transdisciplinary character of the open field days and the dissemination process as a whole.

Overall, three open field days are organized each year in each country, amounting to nine events per year and an overall total of 36 events expected to be organized by the end of the project's lifetime. During 2022 and 2023, two additional events per year in the three countries are organized by local NGOs that have meanwhile been invited to participate in the dissemination efforts of SustainSahel. The involvement of the three NGOs (Agrisud in Senegal, AMSD in Mali, and Tiipaalga in Burkina Faso) brings more practitioners' perspectives to the process, enriching the dialogues and bringing new ideas to the discussions. Furthermore, SustainSahel is largely benefitting from the NGO's own networks of farmers and other stakeholders, resulting in the expansion of the communities of practice.

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The three NGOs were selected based on their experience with crop-shrub-livestock innovations aligned with the purpose of SustainSahel and also considering the extent to which they already work with farmers in a participatory way. The twelve extra events organized by the three NGOs in the project's intervention areas bring the total of expected dissemination events to 48 by 2025.

Two of the yearly dissemination events are organized by farmers' associations and one by the research institutions. The open field days will bring farmers to both on-farm and on-station trials, allowing them to visually assess the results of the different treatments under controlled conditions but also in the real world. At each site, 30 to 40 lead farmers are invited to the different dissemination events, each of them representing a different village. The lead farmers are expected to learn the disseminated techniques and set up their own demonstration plots, if applicable, so that their fellow farmers can learn the techniques from them, thus originating a cascading dissemination process capable of geographically expanding the outreach of the disseminated techniques. The lead farmers are visited at least twice by trained local extension officers engaged in SustainSahel, in order to monitor the implementation and assess the quality of the application of the techniques.

Besides the lead farmers, other stakeholders participate in the open field days, such as local extension officers, members of the innovation platforms, local traditional leaders and other farmers from the village where the event takes place. The participation of IP members enables the creation of a direct bridge between the IP process and the dissemination process, which is expected to enrich the IP discussions about the techniques tested in a participatory way with farmers. On the other hand, the outcomes of the discussions of the IPs are expected to contribute to improving the implementation of the techniques and of the dissemination process itself, in an iterative way. WhatsApp groups in each country facilitate the communication between IP members, researchers, extension officers and farmers' representatives.

SustainSahel is investing in an early start of the dissemination process, which is expected to lay the ground for the improved adoption of the tested and disseminated techniques after the project is finished. The continuous learning process with all of the above-mentioned stakeholders is considered important in a context of very low literacy rates, enabling farmers to integrate new knowledge over the years, while actively participating in the implementation and dissemination processes. An early start is also aligned with the project's initial intention of combining dissemination with an educational component, sharing already existing knowledge about crop-shrub-livestock integration approaches with farmers.

The use of videos to reinforce this aspect is considered appropriate in a context of low literacy rates and a general lack of access to existing knowledge. Furthermore, videos provide a unique way to reach women and the youth, which are traditionally more prone to be excluded from access to relevant agricultural information. The collaboration with Access Agriculture helps identify relevant existing videos related to crop-shrub-livestock integration. The videos have been translated into local languages and will be shared via Bluetooth with farmers, the large majority of which possess a mobile phone that can read videos. The use of this sort of ICT makes it easier for women and the youth to have access to this type of information. Additionally, it creates a new and intriguing situation: since technological literacy is higher among the youth, the older farmers, who traditionally control most of the access to new agricultural knowledge, frequently become dependent on the younger family members to visualize and transfer videos, thus bridging different generations in a collaborative way.

Apart from translating existing videos into local languages and sharing them with farmers, the project will carry out the production of new videos portraying CSL practices. The availability of relevant videos on these practices has been identified to be clearly insufficient, providing an opportunity to fill in the gap and produce innovative content that can be useful for other geographical areas as well, especially considering that the close collaboration with Access Agriculture will enable the translation of such videos into other local languages and its wide distribution. The use of smart projectors in the project's activities also contributes to this effort, since they are connected with Access Agriculture's video database.

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Regardless of a stronger focus on local dissemination and a continuous learning process involving different partners in a transdisciplinary co-creation of new knowledge and its applicability, SustainSahel will also carry out dissemination activities at different levels. A contribution to the African Organic Agriculture Training Manual is seen as a way to fill in the perceived gap the available manuals and materials usually have regarding more systemic approaches such as CSL practices. Local communication channels will be used to diffuse the project’s results and main accomplishments, and to gain visibility on a national level. Different kinds of meetings, workshops and a project final conference will be other tools to disseminate the project’s results to a wider audience. A summary of the main dissemination activities and used tools is provided in table 2.

Table 2. Summary of the core dissemination activities and tools, aims & progress measures

Description	Aims	Current status
Open field days		
A transdisciplinary and cross-WP strategy to disseminate CSL practices is developed in all 7 sites. The events require months of planning and a very close collaboration between FiBL, CSE, farmers’ organizations and research institutions. A detailed local dissemination action plan was established in order to clarify the methodologies and roles of each institution – it is kept up to date (see Annex B).	To disseminate appropriate crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices in the seven project sites of the project and empower smallholder farmers to become the owners and disseminators of the practices themselves, in all of the project sites.	Six out of a total expected 48 dissemination events already took place in the three countries. Three more events in each country will be organized by the end of 2022. The contact between IPs and the local organizers of the dissemination process is established.
Events with NGOs (2 per year, per country)		
Dissemination events in collaboration with SustainSahel partners regarding CSL techniques, local food products and innovative agroecological and organic practices. A total of 12 events in 2022 and 2023.	To complement SustainSahel’s dissemination approach, expanding the outreach of the project’s messages and also capitalizing on a practitioners’ approach as well as on new farmers’ and stakeholders’ networks.	Three out of twelve events have been organized. Nurseries have been established in the intervention areas in all three countries, contributing to providing tree seedlings to farmers involved in the project.
Educational videos to disseminate CSL practices		
Translation of relevant existing videos from AA platform into relevant local languages. Public screenings of agricultural learning videos facilitate debate of different practices in an accessible language for farmers	Providing accessible knowledge on CSL practices to farmers, especially relevant to women and the youth, typically excluded from main information sources. Newly translated videos are made available in online platforms.	Nine existing videos related to CSL practices were identified and translated into the five main languages of SustainSahel sites. The videos will be shared with all lead farmers, IP members, and other farmers associated with the project,

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		with a special focus on women and youth.
Production of new videos regarding CSL practices		
Access Agriculture will collaborate with the project's partners to produce between 3 and new 5 videos (depending on the complexity and associated costs) portraying innovative practices tested by the project. FiBL and CSE are committed to produce further videos if the available material justifies.	The new videos will fill in the gap in the current lack of availability of relevant videos regarding CSL practices in the Sahel. The videos will be translated into local languages and made available in AA's website and AgTube.	A short list of CSL practices tested by the project will be compiled by all partners (with the participation of farmers) by the end of the second trimester of 2023. The first steps in video production will take place in the last trimester of 2023.
Contribute to African Organic Agriculture Training Manual		
A new chapter will be created about shrub inclusion into farming systems	To further disseminate the knowledge produced in the project.	The chapter will be written later in the project
Local communication channels		
To promote and communicate the project's outcomes via local channels	Utilise internal and external project partnerships to 'amplify' the major messages of the project.	1 article has been published in a national newspaper in Mali, 1 in Switzerland and 1 on Global Forum on Agricultural Research and Innovation Blog.
Executive summary on CSL systems in Sahel		
A visually appealing catalogue summarising the knowledge about each individual Crops, Shrub and Livestock investigated in the project, as well as the most effective combinations.	Preserve the knowledge of the project and disseminate it to relevant stakeholder.	Ideas in development.
Direct and Outreach Meetings – EU policy-advocacy dissemination		
For all stakeholders Africa/EU Direct bi-lateral meetings - with key agencies concerned with Africa/EU/SDG agri systems dialogue	To drive effective engagement and co-operation with the most appropriate agencies, organisations, individuals relevant to the project's aims and objectives in order to raise awareness, create understanding and ensure that the project's activity, progress and results are taken into account in forward planning, review and establishment of new and revised protocols and	<i>Quantitative:</i> Number of meetings organised – 10 - 20 planned and numbers of most appropriate, influential individuals attend, personal contacts secured, and the number of E-news sign ups generated as a result. <i>Qualitative:</i> follow up actions secured, written record of Sustain Sahel included in minutes and papers,

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<p>Sector specific & scientific meetings Project partners will attend their own sector relevant meetings and present and/or attend to promote the project, its aims & objectives, progress, and results</p>	<p>recommendations and when establishing research priorities.</p> <p>Partners will create a priority list of the most appropriate and relevant organisations for their area of work, plus each organisation's pattern of committee and general meetings which they will seek to attend and at which they will have opportunities to present & share information on Sustain Sahel. A calendar of events at which the project will be represented will be generated from this list, alongside a mapping of the geographies and project topics covered through these events. Prioritization will result in agreement as to which events/meetings the project will attend in terms of exhibition and information tables, requiring appropriate support from the co-ordination team.</p>	<p>invitations received to attend further/follow-up discussions.</p> <p><i>Quantitative:</i> Number of organizational events and meetings to be covered; together with appropriate range of scientific/practical subject areas. Number of engagements as a result of attendance in e-news sign-ups, social media posts.</p> <p><i>Qualitative:</i> feedback on reception of information and level of engagement with attendees at presentations, discussions or stands. Feedback from presenters/attendees on materials and engagement activities provided / available.</p>
<p>International Project Final Conference</p>		
<p>Present the work of Sustain Sahel overall marking the end of the funded period. External aligned chairs, speakers, and chairs to be selected for programme inclusion alongside local advocates.</p>	<p>Based on the project's programme, methodology and scientific and practical results this event will focus key content on two industry sector developments and present a united (consensus) opinion on the innovation under discussion. The materials and features generated for the Exhibition and Gallery will be utilised as appropriate.</p>	<p>...</p>
<p>Scientific publications</p>		
<p>These are highly prized as they confirm the authority, validity</p>	<p>Partners upload their scientific publications on the SharePoint and open access repositories,</p>	<p>Expected mainly from year 4 of the project.</p>

and innovation built into the project’s plan and ambitions.	where they are then highlighted and promoted via project and partner communication. WVP8 supervises the repository and guides partners in the process.	
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6. Synergies with other work packages

The communication and dissemination activities rely to a great extent on content provided by local partners. FiBL is in constant contact with the local partners and CSE is providing a direct bridge between the local partners, farmers, and FiBL. Stories from the field are thus collected and communicated to the world via the project’s website, social media, newsletter, and articles. A strong cross-work package approach is necessary to fully capture the transdisciplinary nature of the activities developed on the ground.

The local dissemination strategy requires the concerted participation of all partners, across countries and work packages. WVP4, WVP5, WVP6, and WVP7 are expected to contribute with insightful new messages that can be transmitted to farmers and the IPs. WVP2 coordinates the IP process and it is expected that there will be strong links between the IP discussions and the dissemination process, as the two hold the potential to inform each other and contribute to each other’s success through an iterative approach. This close collaboration will allow the build-up of well-informed communities of practice, which can take up the messages brought by previous projects and the new lessons learned by SustainSahel and bring a solution-oriented discussion to a new level.

The adoption studies carried out by WVP3 will take place in Koulikoro (Mali) and Niakhar (Senegal), requiring a close collaboration between the local dissemination actors and the WVP3 process. The lead farmers in the two sites will represent the so-called “intervention villages”, in opposition to the “control villages” where no dissemination will take place. After the endline survey is carried out by WVP3 in both Niakhar and Koulikoro, the control villages will also actively receive information about the project’s main messages, for example through the invitation of key farmers to demonstration plots, radio programs and sharing of videos.

7. Summary list of stakeholders, objectives and tools to drive impact

The table below lays out the target stakeholder groups, the objectives (as outlined in chapter 2) the activities themselves plus the Work Packages and partners involved.

Table 3. Stakeholders, objectives, messages, and communication actions

Target group	Objectives – basis for messages	Communications activities & materials
Farmers, extension workers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide first-hand experience in applying novel techniques • Improve knowledge regarding availability of options to reduce 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise at least 36 open-field days with demonstration & engagement activities at different field sites

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	<p>tillage and maintain/improve soil health and productivity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve knowledge on practical application of CSL systems and their relevance for improved resource use efficiency (i.e. water, nutrients) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Twelve events with NGOs during 2022 and 2023 involving practitioners, advisers & representation of men, women, youth & all agricultural workers • Production of new project videos relevant for the Sahel area • Integration of the IP and local dissemination processes to establish well-informed communities of practice • Project and partners' websites holding accessible information/demonstration of emerging and novel techniques • Produce at least 10 articles in partners' newsletters, magazines, and other publications to cascade information (in French and English) • Project end-user materials including EIP-AGRI Practice abstracts and video/audio materials (in French and English) • Final Sustain Sahel conference held in Brussels and replicated Africa side with recordings from the initial meeting. • Provide at least 4 study visits for students with obligations to cascade information • Create a new section in African Organic Agriculture Training Manual on shrub inclusion into farming systems for reference and cascade to advisory services and practitioners
<p>Value chain /market actors at all levels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate the benefits to these actors of change & work of Sustain Sahel to enhance and deliver sustainability • Collate and address the challenges to implementing change and instigate debate as to how these challenges can be addressed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve whole value chain and market influencers in IPs plus direct meetings as required • Secure contacts to ensure they 'Stay in Touch' and receive invitations to appropriate project events and initiatives
<p>Public authorities and policymakers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase availability of firsthand information based on project progress and results related to CSL systems in a variety of accessible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce accessible executive summary on CSL systems in Sahel in appropriate languages

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	<p>formats – online, visual, interactive, briefings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform policy recommendations direct via meetings and workshops to aid design of policies to overcome obstacles and thus increase adoption of sustainable intensification using shrubs/trees and livestock as appropriate. • Improve knowledge, awareness and increase acceptability of alternative CSL management approaches and their impact through sharing improved evidence base from project trials and practice and communicating widely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the most appropriate policy-making bodies in Senegal, Burkina Faso and Mali with which to build engagement, share briefings and organise workshops • Organise workshop in Brussels on adoption of CSL systems in Sahel • Create roadmap for policymakers on improving adoption of CSL systems in Sahel • Arrange 5-10 stakeholder meetings in Brussels throughout funded time to present project progress and results utilising the authentic voices of practitioners • Communicate project progress & outputs during direct meetings with EC, appropriate DGs and agencies • Arrange policy-based session with presentations and debate at final Sustain Sahel conference involving policy players at regional, national, and European levels.
<p>Scientific community, including students</p>	<p>Improve scientific knowledge and generate an updated state of the art regarding the CSL systems</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of project progress and results to a minimum of one scientific conference per partner and per WVP with the most appropriate events and timings established in advance and well underway by project year 4. Consideration to be given to the primary languages utilised at these events & ensure French as well as English is accommodated at such events. • Publication of project results in at least 7 peer-reviewed journals selected to deliver top impact and to engage the widest range of interested parties – to be published Open Access. • To upload project results to the EU's new Open Research Access portal for easy access • Organise Sustain Sahel final conference in Brussels based on scientific results – to be recorded and made available online to ensure widest cascade and utilisation. A parallel event to be organised in Africa

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		utilising the recording of the Bxls conference as appropriate.
The media and general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase awareness about the efforts invested in sustainable intensification and CSL systems in particular and their role in sustainable development. • Create awareness of availability of alternative solutions (progress & success stories based on story-telling). • Create awareness of availability of sustainable strategies to be adopted in Sahel farming systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public website – segmented to appeal to different audiences and regularly updated and refreshed • 18 articles in national magazines and journals in national languages. • 2 annual ‘news stories’ to be distributed through participants’ channels (websites, magazines etc.). • Contributions to activities of the H2020-SFS 33, partnering and devising initiatives in common with aligned projects,
All stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of the project. • Present the aims of the project. • Describe the procedure for different target groups to receive information from the project, and to participate in initiatives and interact on different topics of the project at different times 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public website updated and engaging and distribution of newsletters • Media releases & articles • Social media of project partners to support cascade project engagement and communication. • Exhibition of visual/video/audio materials generated by project (Gallery, online & onward use)

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) resulting from C&D activities: All results generated within this WP are subject and ruled by the articles foreseen in Section 3 of the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement signed by all partners where IPR issues are settled. In addition, a IPR has been considered as an important part of SustainSAHEL’s Data Management Plan submitted as Deliverable D1.3.

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<p>T 8.3a</p>	<p>Create, develop, and manage the project's website, comms & outreach channels Lead: FiBL, CSE</p>		<p>D8.6 - website, architecture, internal knowledge hub</p>	<p>Continuous development of website & collection/curation of content for website, social channels. Editorial schedules to be created to ensure regular updates & refreshes of the website and accounts Core set of templates created and updated/expanded as necessary for project and partner use. Analytics to be collected continuously and collated/presented at Steering Committee and General Assembly meetings as appropriate. Website to host a newsletter facility to enable contacts to sign up to database. Social media also to push for registrations. All partners to co-operate in securing 'sign ups'. Newsletter to be issued regularly with 15 planned editions across the life of the project.</p>		
<p>T 8.3b</p>	<p>Media & social media: set up development & management Lead: FiBL, CSE</p>	<p>Set up of media lists and social media accounts. Continuous research & refinement of contacts lists including those with allied projects & agencies & funders. On-going planning, content development & delivery of content across social media accounts. All partners to provide content. Creation, despatch and follow up of press releases to highlight key points in project development (2 releases to be issued as a minimum each year). Attention to dual language (Eng./Fr) and use of further local languages as appropriate.</p>				
<p>T 8.4a</p>	<p>Open Field Days Lead: CSE, CPF, AOPP and CNCR</p>		<p>Planning, development & delivery of first Open Field Days</p>	<p>D8.7 Open Field Day Events & Reports - Part I</p>	<p>Review of First Open Field Days & Planning, development & delivery for Second Open Field Days events</p>	<p>D8.8 Open Field Day Events & Reports - Part II</p>
<p>T 8.4b</p>	<p>Speaking and attendance at target African, European and International meetings Lead: FiBL-EU</p>		<p>Pro-active identification of priority target events in Africa, Europe & world-wide appropriate for project to attend, speak at, have a formal presence. Reactive consideration of events to attend dependent on budget. Partners to attend 'usual' professional events (online and/or in person) & cascade project information utilising available project materials.</p>			<p>D8.9 Report on Bi-lateral Policy Meetings</p>
<p>T 8.5</p>	<p>Policy and practice engagement to drive utilization and impact at EU level and Final conference</p>				<p>Planning, preparation for final conference Planning, preparation for Final Conference - duplicate event Africa side- location to be agreed and/or online</p>	<p>Final conference</p>

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	Lead: FiBL- EU/FiBL, CSE				
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Annex A

Table A-1. List of WP8 potential partnerships. The list is used by WP8 to keep track of partnerships made or in development.

This table will develop and change over time. Table A-2 provides more details regarding the projects listed.

Level	Organisation name and contact	Current collaboration and/or future plans
National – country:		
Senegal	TaFAé <i>Multi-actor task force for the promotion of agroecology in Senegal</i>	Current: Future:
	ENDA Pronat - <i>Improving and Securing Access to Land for Rural Women in Senegal</i>	Current: Future:
	FIARA / Foire Internationale de l'Agriculture et des Ressources Animales <i>Congress / Fairs of producers – Senegal /CNCR organises</i>	Current: Future:
	FENAB - <i>Fédération Nationale pour l'Agriculture Biologique, Senegal</i> <i>Network, resources, events</i>	Current: Future:
	APAF - <i>Association pour la Promotion de l'Agroforesterie et de la Foresterie – Sénégal</i> <i>Africa wide promotion/ support of novel approaches to agroforestry</i>	Current: Future:
	PFONGUE- Platform of European NGOs in Senegal <i>Cross disciplinary opportunities to share knowledge</i>	
Mali	CNOP - Coordination Nationale des Organisations Paysannes, Mali Enables farmers' organizations in Mali to contribute to clear vision of Malian agriculture & coherent agricultural policy centered on family farms.	
Burkina Faso		
Regional/West Africa	ROPFA – <i>peasant/farmer organisations in W Africa</i>	
	CILSS – <i>Inter Etats dans le Sahel</i> <i>Permanent Inter-State Committee for Drought Control in the Sahel</i>	
	PPZS - <i>Pastoralisme en zones sèches</i> <i>ISRA/CIRAD – networking</i>	
	CORAF – <i>Research & Innovation Platforms</i> <i>Coordinate/ facilitate ground-breaking/ cutting-edge research outputs unlocking the agricultural potential West/Central Africa.</i>	
Pan-Africa	ACT – <i>African Conservation Tillage Network</i> <i>Network, resources, events</i>	Current: Future:
	IITA – <i>International Institute Tropical Agriculture (Nigeria)</i> <i>research partnership facilitates agricultural solutions</i>	Current: Future:
	ICRAF – <i>World Agroforestry (Kenya)</i> <i>Network, regional/national initiatives – World Congress on Agroforestry</i>	Current: Future:
	ILRI – <i>International Livestock Research Organisation</i> <i>Better lives through livestock in developing countries.</i>	Current: Future:
	FARA – <i>Forum for Agricultural Research in Africa</i> <i>Co-ordination & collaboration</i>	Current: Future:
	<i>Future Africa Forum Next generation involvement in Policy</i>	Current: Future:
	CIRAD – <i>Agricultural Research for Development – based in France : Coastal West Africa website</i>	Current: Future:
Project	SustInAfrica: Sustainable intensification of food production through resilient farming systems in West & North Africa https://www.sustinafrica.com/	Current: Future:
	EWVA-BELT: Linking East and West African farming systems experience into a BELT of sustainable intensification https://www.ewabelt.eu/	
	Soils4Africa : Soil Information System for Africa https://www.soils4africa-h2020.eu/	
	CaSSECS: <i>Carbon Sequestration and greenhouse gas emissions in (agro) Sylvopastoral Ecosystems in the Sahelian CILSS States</i> https://www.cassecs.org/	
	FAIR Sahel: <i>Fostering an Agroecological Intensification to improve farmers' resilience in Sahel</i> https://www.fair-sahel.org/	

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	UPSCALERS: Upscaling Site-Specific Climate-smart Agriculture and Land use practices to Enhance Regional Production Systems in West-Africa https://upscale-h2020.eu/	
	RAMSES II: Roles of Agroforestry in sustainable intensification of small farMs and food SEcurity for Socletes in West Africa https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects/partnership/37	
	AfriCultuReS: Enhancing Food Security in AFRican AgriCULTURAL Systems with the Support of REMote Sensing https://africultures.ifca.es/	
European	EC Task Force Rural Africa <i>Created 2018 to advise EC on how best to contribute to sustainable development in Africa's agri-food sector/rural economy</i>	
EU-AU partnerships	FNSSA – EU/Africa R&I on food & national security	
	EU-Africa High Level Policy Dialogue (HLPD) <i>Platform for regular exchange on Science, Tech, Innovation (STI)</i>	
	The EU-Africa Partnership: African Union <i>Formal political channel through which EU & Africa work together & define cooperative relationship</i>	
	LEAP Agri (ERA-Net) <i>Food & nutrition security</i>	
	EU DGs – DevCO & AGRI, EEAS & EP:DEVE, including DeSIRA program <i>Co-operation, collaboration on research initiatives</i>	
	OACPs – Organisation of Africa, Caribbean & Pacific Group of States Secretariat <i>(formerly ACP)- Networking, representation, funding & support</i> Active in: Burkina Faso, Mali, Senegal http://www.acp.int/	
Think Tanks/Policy ex.EU/Africa	ReSAKSS-West Africa <i>Regional strategic analyses and knowledge support system – comprehensive datasets: Africa wide & West Africa</i>	
	FANRPAN - Policy analyses network <i>Partnerships, networks, based in S Africa</i>	
	Chatham House : Africa programme <i>Inclusive economic growth – based in UK</i>	
International	UN – FAO Africa Family Farming & Agroecology Community of Practice (CoP) https://dgroups.org/faofamilyfarming/agroecologyafrica/	Current: share the project newsletter with the CoP Future: share relevant SS outputs (e.g., website news items, blog posts, videos, etc.) with CoP
	UN – FAO Family Farming Knowledge Platform https://www.fao.org/family-farming/resources	Current: submit all relevant SS outputs (e.g., website newsletter, blog posts, videos, etc.) in resource database Future: feature article in FFKP newsletter about results from project, videos, etc.
	UN – FAO Agroecology Knowledge Hub https://www.fao.org/agroecology/en/	Current: Project description and project newsletters feature in database Future: feature article in newsletter about results from project, videos, etc.
	UN – CCD Convention to Combat Desertification <i>CRIC19, Knowledge Hub</i> https://knowledge.unccd.int/	Future: contribute to the Knowledge Hub – to discuss if relevant.

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Table A-2. Details of the Organisations featured in table A-1.

The following topics and areas of research have been identified that focus on sustainable intensification and the livelihoods of farmers in sub-Saharan Africa. The SustainSAHEL will liaise closely with these initiatives and identify common areas of work, devising a plan for future and synergetic collaborations.

Project title	Start date	End date	Coordinator	Main Funder	Locations	Links
SustInAfrica: Sustainable intensification of food production through resilient farming systems in West & North Africa	01.09.2020	31.08.2025	LUKE (Finland)	(DG RTD) (H2020)	Ghana - Burkina Faso - Niger - Egypt - Tunisia	https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects/214 https://www.sustinafrica.com/
EWA-BELT: Linking East and West African farming systems experience into a BELT of sustainable intensification	01.10.2020	30.09.2024	University of Sassari (Italy)	(DG RTD) (H2020)	Burkina Faso - Ghana - Sierra Leone - Ethiopia - Kenya - Tanzania, United Republic of	https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects/221 https://www.ewabelt.eu/ https://www.cranfield.ac.uk/research-projects/ewa-belt
Soils4Africa : Soil Information System for Africa	01.06.2020	31.05.2024	ISRIC - World soil information	(DG RTD) (H2020)		https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects/205 https://www.soils4africa-h2020.eu/
CaSSECS: Carbon Sequestration and greenhouse gas emissions in (agro) Sylvopastoral Ecosystems in the Sahelian CILSS States	01.01.2020	31.12.2023	ISRA	(DG DEVCO)	Senegal - Burkina Faso - Niger - Mali - Chad - Mauritania	https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects/220 https://www.cassecs.org/

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Project title	Start date	End date	Coordinator	Main Funder	Locations	Links
FAIR Sahel: Fostering an Agroecological Intensification to improve farmers' resilience in Sahel	01.01.2020	31.12.2023	CIRAD	(DG DEVCO)	Burkina Faso - Mali - Senegal	https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/sites/default/files/media/fair_sahel_desira_2020.pdf https://www.fair-sahel.org/
UPSCALERS: Upscaling Site-Specific Climate-smart Agriculture and Land use practices to Enhance Regional Production Systems in West-Africa	01.02.2018	31.01.2021	West African Science Service Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use (WASCAL) (Ghana)	African Union Commission (AURG 2)	Burkina Faso - Mali - Kenya	https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects/85 https://upscale-h2020.eu/
RAMSES II: Roles of Agroforestry in sustainable intensification of small farMs and food SEcurity for Socityles in West Africa	01.09.2018	31.08.2021	IRD	ERA-Net Cofund (LEAP-Agri)	Senegal - Burkina Faso	https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects/37 https://josianeseghieri.wixsite.com/ramsesii
AfriCultuReS: Enhancing Food Security in AFRican AgriCULTUral Systems with the Support of REmote Sensing	01.11.2017	31.10.2021	GMV Aerospace and Defense (Spain)	(DG RTD) (H2020)	Ghana - Niger	https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects/5 https://www.africultures.eu/

Annex B - Local dissemination action plan

Local Dissemination Action plan

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Summary & Objectives

SustainSahel seeks to enhance the resilience of farming systems in the Sahel through the study and dissemination of appropriate crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices. This is achieved through a transdisciplinary approach: the integration of social and natural sciences in close collaboration with smallholder farmers. **The dissemination of appropriate practices is one of the core cross-WP activities in the project, involving all actors and a very close collaboration between farmers' organizations and research institutions in each partner country.**

The local dissemination action plan is outlined in the present document with the intention of clarifying the methodologies and the roles of each institution in the process. All partner institutions are expected to contribute to the activities and report on the results of each activity. Farmers' associations and research institutions in particular are expected to drive the processes outlined in these guidelines, and any doubts can be clarified with the overall coordination at FiBL.

The main objectives of the local dissemination activities are:

- 1- **To disseminate appropriate crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices** in the 7 project sites of the project: Ouarkhokh, Niakhar, Koussanar (Senegal); Koulikoro, Sikasso (Mali); Saria, Yilou (Burkina Faso) – This task is jointly coordinated by the partner institutions in each country with the overview coordination of FiBL as outlined in sections 2 and 4 of this document;
- 2- **To study the socio-economic impact of the disseminated crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices** in 2 of the project sites: Niakhar (Senegal) and Koulikoro (Mali) – This particular task is coordinated by WP3 and described in section 3 of this document.
- 3- **To empower smallholder farmers to become the owners and disseminators of the practices themselves, in all of the project sites** – This task is achieved through the direct involvement of lead farmers and other partners, as described in sections 2 and 4 of this document.

The dissemination approach can be summarized as in figure 1.

RESEAU DE VULGARISATION LOCALE

Niakhar & Koulikoro

Villages de démonstration (site CEP) sont associées à la plate-forme d'innovation

Un nombre (~40) de villages d'intervention (avec producteurs relais) sont associées à des villages de démonstration (site CEP)

Plate-forme d'innovation > Coordination

- Catalyseur d'innovation
- Échange entre les chercheurs et les représentants des agriculteurs/de la chaîne de valeur

Villages de démonstration > Champs écoles producteurs (CEP)

- Apprentissage basée sur démonstrations et renforcement des capacités (dans les CEP).
- Activités pour les producteurs des villages de démonstration et participation d'un producteur relais (agriculteur leader) de chaque villages d'intervention (environ 40).

Villages d'intervention > Multiplication

- Apprentissage par la multiplication des connaissances
- Les producteurs relais participant aux démonstrations et aux CEP partagent leurs connaissances avec les autres producteurs dans leurs villages (villages d'intervention).

Figure 1. Local dissemination approach – Sustain Sahel.

Action plan in 8 main steps

The implementation of the local dissemination activities must take into account the specificities of each site due to the different nature of the particular crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices that will be studied in each site. These specificities are defined and managed locally by each team. However, the general action plan that applies to all local dissemination activities can be summarized in the following 8 steps:

1. **Set-up team meetings** with the responsible project members (see the tables in Annex I and II) in order to plan the local dissemination activities in each country: the roles of each institution and of each individual involved should be clear from the beginning.
2. **Interact with WP2** leaders to 1) clarify who are the IP members in the site, 2) where exactly they are located and 3) make sure they are involved in the activities and that these are discussed by them. Specifically for the sites of Niakhar and Koulikoro, **interactions with WP3** are essential.
3. **Select the core villages**, considering the locations where the project interventions are implemented and where the IP members/meetings are located. The core villages will be the centre of the dissemination activities for the site between 2022 and 2025.
4. **Elaborate a detailed timeline** for each of the sites in your country, clearly indicating the optimal dates and the number of the dissemination activities. Farmers' organisations and research institutions in each country are expected to work together in defining the timeline for each site.
5. **Identify 40 lead farmers** in each site. These farmers should come from 40 different villages around the core villages, considering the site boundaries defined by WP2. The lead farmers are

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expected to participate in all of the dissemination activities and bring the information and implementation (if applied) of the practices back to their own villages. For Niakhar and Koulikoro, the lead farmers must come only from the selected intervention villages.

6. **Outline a detailed budget** for all dissemination activities and clarify the contributions of each institution in terms of time allocated and funds for the activities (see section 6 of this document).
7. **Implement the dissemination activities** throughout the project time according to the jointly elaborated timeline and including the activities outlined in section 4. For each activity, it is important to have clear responsible persons and institutions.
8. **Report and review** the experiences internally and share the information with other countries, as well as with the overall coordination at FiBL. This will provide learning to all teams and allow to improve the approach by detecting best dissemination practices and learning from mistakes.
9. **Adapt** (if necessary) the specific activities for which the internal review concludes that are not fully adapted to the local reality. This can be seen as a learning process and is expected to be dynamic and not static throughout the years. Adaptations should be discussed internally between institutions, with WP2 and WP3 (for Niakhar and Koulikoro) and with the overall coordination at FiBL.

The special cases of Niakhar (Senegal) and Koulikoro (Mali)

Due to an already existing baseline dataset from a previous project, the two project sites of Niakhar and Koulikoro have been selected to evaluate the socio-economic impact and the adoptability of the different crop-shrub/tree-livestock practices that are being tested and promoted in the sites. This study will be coordinated by WP3 and provides **a unique opportunity to understand the real impact of the SustainSahel's dissemination activities**, especially in terms of knowledge transfer and potential to lead to partial or full adoption of the disseminated practices. These new insights are important to all partners, not only for upcoming collaborations with farmers but also for future projects and dissemination strategies.

As with all other 5 sites, the sites of Niakhar and Koulikoro will also follow the steps described in section 2, with the identification of 40 lead farmers representing 40 villages around the core villages where the dissemination activities will take place, although for the two sites this selection is based on randomisation. In Niakhar and Koulikoro, in addition to the intervention group, a group of other 40 villages will be defined as the control group, which will have no contact with any dissemination activity developed by the project. The research design of the randomised controlled trial requires that both intervention and control villages are randomly selected. After two years of dissemination activities (2022 and 2023), an endline survey will be carried out in the 80 villages (40 villages exposed to dissemination activities + 40 control villages) in the two sites in 2024. This will allow to compare the results and analyse the impact of the dissemination activities. Between 2022 and the endline survey in 2024, it will be important to prevent any interaction between the project activities and the villages in the control group. After the endline survey takes place in 2024, the dissemination activities can include the control villages.

For Niakhar, the core villages with demonstration trials are Sob, Diohine and Sanghaie. The 40 villages from which lead farmers will be invited (intervention villages) and the control villages are identified in figure 1 in blue and red, respectively.

Figure 2. Map of the 40 intervention villages (in blue) and the 40 control villages (in red) for the site of Niakhar.

For Koulikoro, 5 on-farm field trials have been implemented in the core villages of Tietiguila, Tanabougou and Feya. The identification of the exact 40 intervention and control villages is yet to be finalized. The preliminary map with the survey sites for Koulikoro can be seen in figure 2.

Figure 3. Preliminary map of the survey sites for Koulikoro.

List of specific activities and responsible individuals/institutions

This list of activities is to be implemented in each site, even though adaptations might be needed in some cases due to site-specific and practice-specific characteristics. The activities should be informed by the insights generated by the MARP and IP discussions of WVP2. In turn, the activities and their results should also be brought to these discussions in order to assess their potential and performance.

Activity 1. Continuous coaching of a local group of extension officers

A group of local extension officers (between 2 and 5 extension officers, depending on availability and resources) active in the region should be recruited and jointly trained by the farmers' associations and research institutions in each site. The research institutions should make sure that the extension officers have an in-depth understanding of the general goals of SustainSahel and the specific goals of each practice that is being locally studied and disseminated. The extension officers will then be assigned with the task of visiting the 40 lead farmers during the rainy season (two to three times) in order to guide them on the implementation of the practices and follow-up on the development with pictures. The main idea is to reinforce the lessons learned during the first session of activity 2, which takes place in March, and give the

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lead farmers the possibility to clarify doubts and deepen their understanding. Besides the field visits, the extension officers are expected to be in contact with the lead farmers through phone calls and SMS. The extension officers will report the results of their activities to the site lead, who will use the information for the yearly report.

Activity 2. Farmer Field Days in the on-farm trials (2 per year: March and September)

This activity is recommended to take place twice per year, once in March, before farmers prepare their fields, and once in September, when the vegetative stage of the crops is at their peak. The first event, in March, has a strong emphasis on the implementation of the practices while the event in September has a strong focus on the analysis of the observed results before harvest. The activity should count with 1) farmers from the hosting village, 2) the 40 lead farmers of the intervention villages, 3) the site's IP members, 4) the local group of extension officers and 5) the researchers and students involved. This activity is expected to last one morning. All participants receive a certificate if they attend both events.

Activity 3. Farmer Field Days in the on-station trials (1 per year: September)

This activity is recommended to take place once per year in September, for the reasons stated above. With a similar structure as activity 2, this activity will involve the same actors but will take place in the research station and be guided by the research partners. The farmers will be given the chance to discuss the observed results in the light of what they have seen during activity 2.

Activity 4. Engagement of lead farmers and knowledge sharing in intervention villages

This activity will be supported by activity 1 and intends to reinforce the engagement and motivation of lead farmers along the whole dissemination period, between 2022 and 2025. It is recommended that the lead farmers receive support from extension officers and researchers on how to share acquired knowledge and implement the disseminated practices in order to enable them to establish demonstration plots of their own in their villages. The quality of implementation can be assessed through the pictures that the extension officers will take during their visits. A jury selected for each site can vote the three best demonstration plots by lead farmers each year. The winners receive a small grant or equipment (to be defined by each local team).

Activity 5. Diffusion of learning materials

In collaboration with Access Agriculture, different agricultural learning videos aligned with the main messages of SustainSahel will be selected. Because many farmers either own or have access to 3G phones or even smartphones (through a relative) with video and Bluetooth technology, videos will be shared with them. To make this sharing easier, the extension officers mentioned in activity 1 will receive memory cards with the videos, allowing them to bring them on their phones and share with farmers via Bluetooth during their visits. Also, a permanent "video booth" will stay in each core village, where a village inhabitant

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(probably a mobile phone repairer or shop owner) will receive memory cards with the selection of videos. Farmers can then come to this “video booth” and ask for a free transfer via Bluetooth. The “video booth” contact receives a small compensation for enabling this video transfer.

Radio campaigns will be part of the dissemination approach (excluding Niakhar and Koulikoro due to concerns that it might affect the study described in section 3), with programs aligned with the main messages of SustainSahel.

For literate farmers, a selection of documents will be available on demand, such as leaflets or field experiment manuals. Visual posters and other products capable of instructing illiterate farmers will also be included. Farmer field school’s manuals and other materials will be made available for extension officers.

Activity 6. Inputs and synergies with other stakeholders

Inputs such as tree seedlings, tree cuttings and bush/tree seeds will be made available to lead farmers and some other participants who wish to implement the disseminated practices. This will depend on the type of disseminated practices in each site and the feasibility of such approach in each context.

In some cases, other external stakeholders (for example New Tree in Burkina Faso) will be invited to join some activities and enhance them by organizing complementary activities, such as cinema sessions, debates and degustation of traditional foods.

Timeline of the activities

The table below shows the recommended yearly timeline of the dissemination activities and it should be the same or with only small agreed amendments between the years. In year 2025, the main difference is that radio can be used in Niakhar and Koulikoro for the first time and the dissemination can be spread to the control villages.

Table 1. General recommended yearly timeline, from 2022 to 2024

Activity 1			—			—		—				
Activity 2			—						—			
Activity 3									—			
Activity 4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Activity 5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Activity 6			—						—			
Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec

Considerations about budget

Farmers associations and research institutions both received budget lines to carry out the activities described in section 4 of this document. The budget lines and their detailed descriptions have been shared with the partners via email.

The detailed budget regarding the yearly activities should be sent to the overall coordination at FiBL by December 2021 and must take into account:

- Activity 1: The cost of recruiting extension officers and train them on the project's goals, including fuel for their transport for the coaching sessions and the three yearly events (shared responsibility between farmers' associations and research institutions).
- Activity 2: The cost of inviting 40 lead farmers to the on-farm farmers' field days, including transport and food, the engagement of extension officers, IP members (responsibility of the farmers' associations) and the engagement of researchers and students (responsibility of the research institutions).
- Activity 3: The cost of inviting 40 lead farmers to the on-station farmers' field days, including transport and food, cost of engagement of researchers and IP members (responsibility of the research institutions).
- Activity 4: Cost of fuel for the two visits of extension officers to the 40 lead farmers during the rainy season (shared responsibility between farmers' associations and research institutions).
- Activity 5: Cost of the "video booth" responsible person in one or more core villages, per year (responsibility of farmers' associations).
- Activity 6: Cost of producing tree seedlings and tree seeds to share with the farmers (responsibility of the research institutions).